

COERCION AND ITS LIMITS: COLONIAL POLICING, NON-COERCIVE IMPROVISATION, AND THE ORIGINS OF HYBRID CONFLICT MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIA’S MIDDLE BELT, 1920S–1960

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Abstract: *Scholarship on colonial policing in Nigeria has focused primarily on how coercive instruments of the colonial state suppressed indigenous governance and entrenched racial hierarchies. This paper shifts the analytical lens from coercion as outcome to coercion as a structurally limited process. Drawing on provincial administrative records and Native Authority court documents from the Endangered Archives Programme at the British Library, supported by oral interviews conducted in Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa states between 2019 and 2021, the paper argues that colonial policing was the dominant but structurally deficient mode of conflict management in the region between the 1920s and independence in 1960. The Native Authority Police (NAP) and military patrols generated resistance, lacked community legitimacy, and were structurally incapable of penetrating inter-group conflicts at the rural community level. This coercive deficit compelled the colonial administration to develop non-coercive mechanisms, specifically administrative arbitration, traditional ruler mediation, and educated elite advocacy, as improvised responses to the limits of force. The paper argues that it was this improvisation, not deliberate hybrid governance design, that produced the tripartite conflict management architecture that postcolonial governments in the Middle Belt inherited. The colonial origins of that architecture have not been systematically traced. This paper supplies the genealogy.*

1. Introduction

In 1912, two British prospectors erected survey beacons on farmland near an Eggon community in the Nasarawa Division of what would become

Nigeria’s Middle Belt. The Eggon believed the beacons were instruments of malevolent magic and had already suffered a run of poor harvests,

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so they killed one of the prospectors. The colonial response was swift and disproportionate: two officers, a lieutenant, and ninety rank-and-file soldiers executed a punitive patrol that left 179 people dead and six villages destroyed or damaged. A collective fine of 6,500 bundles of grain was subsequently imposed on the communities involved. The colonial officer who authorised the patrol defended it as necessary to demonstrate that ‘the white man shall be regarded as sacred.’¹ The Eggon episode is not exceptional. It is representative. Across the Middle Belt between the 1920s and independence in 1960, colonial policing in the Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa provinces operated primarily through coercive force: punitive military patrols, collective fines, arbitrary detention, and the imposition of a Native Authority Police apparatus that indigenous communities associated with Hausa-Fulani dominance rather than impartial governance. Existing scholarship on colonial policing in Nigeria has documented this coercive character extensively. Ahire demonstrated that the police in colonial Nigeria served imperial extraction and political suppression rather than crime control.² Tamuno traced the institutional development of the Nige-

rian Police Force as an instrument of colonial authority.³ More recently, Ikuteyijo and Rotimi have examined the behavioural legacy of colonial policing in contemporary Nigeria.⁴

This paper does not dispute that account. Colonial policing in the Middle Belt was indeed primarily coercive, and that coercion left institutional legacies that shape security relations in the region to the present day. What existing scholarship has not examined is the structural consequence of the limits of coercion: the inability of the Native Authority Police and military patrols to manage inter-group conflict at the community level generated a sustained coercive deficit that compelled the colonial administration to improvise non-coercive supplements. Administrative arbitration, traditional ruler mediation, and the co-optation of educated elites as institutional advocates were not designed as components of a hybrid governance system. They were improvised responses to what force could not do. It is this improvisation that produced the tripartite conflict management architecture that postcolonial governments in the Middle Belt inherited. A note on scope is necessary. This paper’s focus on conflict management is distinct from the question of whether the Native Authority Police

¹David C Dorward, ‘Ritual Warfare and the Colonial Conquest of the Eggon’, *History in Africa* 11 (1984): 83–98, doi:10.2307/3171629; ‘Schedule of Correspondence Relating to the Murder of Mr D A Campbell’, *Endangered Archives Programme*, April 1912, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-4-67>.

²Philip Terdoo Ahire, *Imperial Policing: The Emergence and Role of the Police in Colonial Nigeria, 1860-1960* (Open University Press Buckingham, 1991).

³Tekena N Tamuno, *The Police in Modern Nigeria, 1861-1965: Origins, Development, and Role* (Ibadan University Press, 1970).

⁴Lanre Ikuteyijo and Kemi Rotimi, ‘The Image of Nigeria Police: Lessons from History’, *Journal of Applied Security Research* 9, no. 2 (2014): 221–35.

was effective at ordinary crime management in colonial Plateau Province. A 2022 study by Jonah has argued, drawing on the same provincial records, that the NAP was indeed effective at controlling crime in the Lowland Division.⁵ That may be so. The paper's concern is different: not whether the NAP controlled petty crime but whether coercive mechanisms, broadly construed, could manage the intergroup conflicts between indigenes and settlers, between farmers and herders, and between ethnic minorities and the Hausa-Fulani administrative apparatus that were the defining security challenge of the Middle Belt. The evidence shows they could not, and it is from that failure that the paper's argument proceeds.

The paper draws on archival materials from the Endangered Archives Programme at the British Library, including Plateau Province Annual Reports, Jos Division Quarterly Reports, and Benue Province administrative correspondence from the 1910s to 1960, as well as oral interviews conducted with key informants in Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa states between 2019 and 2021. All interviews were conducted under ethics clearance from the University of Jos. Informants are identified by anonymised codes throughout the paper.

The argument made here engages directly with the recent development in the hybrid security

governance literature for Africa. Bagayoko and Hutchful have argued that understanding hybrid security orders in Africa requires developing thorough knowledge of the socially embedded forms of reciprocity that inform leadership, recruitment, and the functioning of security actors in practice.⁶ This call is an important advance on the earlier Bagayoko, Hutchful, and Luckham framework, which identified hybridity as a structural feature of African security governance but did not trace the historical processes through which those embedded reciprocities came to be.⁷ This paper supplies precisely what the updated framework calls for but does not provide. The *Ardo* and district head mediation system, the collective punishment procedure that required provincial officers of two different territories to negotiate a shared penalty framework, and the role of traditional rulers as mandated arbiters of farmer-herder disputes are not pre-colonial survivals that persisted in spite of colonial rule. They are colonial productions whose origins lie in the specific improvised responses of an under-resourced colonial state to its own coercive limits. While Bagayoko and Hutchful's framework can name the socially embedded reciprocity that characterises contemporary hybrid security governance in the Middle Belt, this paper explains where it originated.

⁵Changwak Emmanuel Jonah, 'Policing the Lowland Axis of the Plateau Province in the Colonial Period, 1926-1960' 11, no. 1 (June 2022).

⁶Niagalé Bagayoko and Eboe Hutchful, 'The Hybridisation of Security', *African Security Sector Network*, 2024.

⁷Niagalé Bagayoko, Eboe Hutchful, and Robin Luckham, 'Hybrid Security Governance in Africa: Rethinking the Foundations of Security, Justice and Legitimate Public Authority', *Conflict, Security and Development* 16, no. 1 (2016): 1–32, doi:10.1080/14678802.2016.1136137.

2. Colonial Policing in the Middle Belt: Coercive Dominance and Its Instruments

The administrative architecture that the British colonial government erected in the Plateau Province was built, from the outset, on an asymmetric logic. Lord Lugard's Indirect Rule model, applied to the northern territories from 1900, used the Fulani-led emirate system as the template for Native Authority governance across Northern Nigeria. That template did not fit a region of over two hundred ethnically distinct and predominantly non-Muslim communities. The colonial administration's solution was to impose the emirate model on stateless and decentralised societies, appointing chiefs where none had previously existed and reorganising diverse communities under single district heads regardless of pre-colonial allegiance.⁸ In Plateau Province, this approach produced eleven indigenous districts governed by appointed chiefs alongside four Hausa village areas administered by headmen with explicit authority over non-indigenous settler populations. The jurisdictional dualism of this arrangement, with indigenous districts governed by co-opted traditional authorities and settler zones governed by Hausa headmen with colonial backing, was the structural foundation on which

conflict management in the Middle Belt was built.

The police apparatus that operated within this structure was the *Dogarai* (later the *Yan Doka*), a force whose name, originally associated with a Hausa emir's bodyguards, signalled its ethnic character to non-Muslim communities from the outset.⁹ For 'pagan' minority communities across the Middle Belt, the *Dogarai* were not a neutral enforcement body. They were considered instruments of Hausa-Fulani sub-colonialism, officers who served the regime rather than the people. Oral tradition in Plateau Province remembers the *Dogarai* as 'mainly Hausa' and associates them with oppression and intimidation. Among the Tiv in Benue Province, the British-inspired witch-hunt campaigns of the 1930s were marred by the excesses of the *Dogari* and *Yan Doka*, whose indiscriminate maltreatment of elders was experienced as anti-Tiv persecution.¹⁰ In Nasarawa, elders from Eggon villages described how troops massacred men, women, and children and robbed farms in the aftermath of colonial punitive patrols.¹¹ These were not isolated grievances. They were the consistent pattern of a coercive apparatus that communities across the Middle Belt experienced as alien and hostile.

⁸Chunun Paul Logams, *The Middle-Belt Movement in Nigerian Political Development: A Study in Political Identity 1949-1967* (Abuja: Centre for Middle-Belt Studies, Nigeria, 2004).

⁹Cecil Geraint Ames, *Gazetteers of the Northern Province of Nigeria* (London: Frank Cass and Company Limited, 1972), 117–20.

¹⁰David Craig Dorward, 'The Development of the British Colonial Administration among the Tiv 1900-1949', *African Affairs* 68, no. 273 (1969): 316–33, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/720655>.

¹¹Jonathan Mamu Ayuba, 'Social and Economic Change in Colonial North-Central Nigeria: The History of Akwanga Division, 1911-1960' (PhD thesis, The University of London, 2007).

The resistance that colonial coercion generated is perhaps the clearest evidence of its structural inadequacy as a conflict management instrument. The Ganawuri, Hos, and Rukuba resisted British conquest through alliances against foreign rule from 1902 onwards. The Tal and Pai of Pankshin perpetrated acts of resistance in 1921. The Montol resisted from 1899 to 1932. The Eggon rose repeatedly between 1912 and 1917. The Afo in Benue resisted in 1922. The Berom and Anaguta rioted against the 1913 Public Lands Acquisition Proclamation.¹² In each case, the colonial administration's response was punitive, consisting of military patrols, collective fines, the imprisonment or deposition of community leaders, and their forced relocations. In each case, the punitive response temporarily suppressed the immediate disturbance while deepening the resentments that would produce the next one. The colonial administration was managing conflict through methods that reproduced it.

The four successive phases of establishing a workable Native Authority administration in Plateau Province between 1900 and the 1930s, spanning Lugard's initial paramount chieftaincy model through Clifford's revisions, Palmer's return to the emirate template, and Cameron's Tanganyikan experiments, were, as the archival records acknowledge, ultimately unsuccessful.¹³

The colonial administration could not establish central paramount chiefs capable of exercising legitimate authority over the province's diverse ethnic groups. Traditions of decentralised governance, oral histories of divergent origins, and the refusal of communities to recognise the sovereignty of imposed chiefs consistently frustrated attempts to build a unified administrative apparatus. The four-phase failure is significant. It means that the colonial administration spent the first three decades of its rule in the Middle Belt attempting and failing to create the institutional precondition for effective coercive governance.

3. The Coercive Deficit: Why Force Could Not Manage Inter-Group Conflict

The structural inadequacy of colonial coercion as a conflict management instrument in the Middle Belt operated along three dimensions: under-resourcing, ethnic compromise, and jurisdictional limitation. The under-resourcing of the coercive apparatus was chronic. The Plateau Province was vast and its terrain formidable; the number of colonial officers and *Yan Doka* officers deployed was never proportionate to the scale of the governance and security challenge. Annual reports from the 1920s through the 1940s document a consistent gap between the demands

¹²Elizabeth Isichei, ed., *Studies in the History of Plateau State, Nigeria* (Chippenham, Wiltshire: Antony Rowe Ltd, 1993), 206–8; 'Police Escort to Montol District Shendam Division [March 31]', *Endangered Archives Programme*, April 1926, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-22-18>; 'Schedule of Correspondence Relating to the Murder of Mr D A Campbell'; 'Benue Prov-

ince Afo Pagans Disturbance', *Endangered Archives Programme*, April 1922, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-4-18>.

¹³Monday Yakiban Mangyvat, *History of Class Formation in the Plateau Province of Nigeria, 1902-1960: The Genesis of the Ruling Class* (Durham: Carolina Academic Press, 2013).

placed on the police and their capacity to respond.¹⁴ The ratio of police officers to population was negligible in rural areas, and even in the divisional headquarters of Jos, Makurdi, and Lafia, police numbers were insufficient to provide consistent enforcement. This resourcing gap meant that coercive responses to intergroup conflict were episodic rather than systemic: the administration could send a punitive patrol after a conflict had erupted but had no capacity for the kind of sustained presence that might prevent escalation.

The ethnic compromise of the NAP was equally debilitating. A police force that non-Muslim communities experienced as an extension of Hausa-Fulani administrative dominance could not function as a neutral arbiter of intergroup disputes in which Hausa settlers were one of the contesting parties. Administrative records from the Jos Division document the consistent alignment of the NAP with the interests of the Hausa administrative apparatus: Native Authority employees were expected to align their employment with membership in the Northern People's Congress, the ruling party of the Northern Region.¹⁵ A police force enrolled in partisan ethnic politics

was structurally incapable of managing the intergroup conflicts that partisan ethnic politics generated.

The jurisdictional limitation was the most fundamental. The Native courts that handled criminal and civil cases within pagan communities were presided over by district heads whose authority was recognised only within their own ethnic community. A 1934 annual report from Plateau Province documented the consequences with unusual candour:

The people of Hos never use the Ganawuri court because it is presided over by the chief of another tribe. For the same reason, the people of Gabong will most unwillingly go to the Naraguta court because their chief, who belongs to the Birom tribe, is not a member.¹⁶

Where inter-group conflict required a neutral forum for adjudication, the colonial court system provided none. The ethnic basis of judicial authority meant that every court was, in the perception of communities that did not recognise its president's legitimacy, an enemy court. The colonial administration had inadvertently created a situation in which the formal mechanisms of conflict management were accessible only within

14'Annual Report Plateau Province Department Reports [1934]' (British Library, EAP532/1/3/12, n.d.), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-3-12>; 'Bauchi Province Annual Report [December 31]' (British Library, 1951), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-20-8>.

15'Jos Division Plateau Province Annual Report', *Endangered Archives Programme*, April 1943, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-20->

13#?xywh=-586%2C-206%2C3745%2C4106; Godwin A Vaaseh, 'Ethnic Politics and Conflicts in Nigeria's First Republic: The Misuse of Local Administrative Police Forces (NAPFS) and the Tiv Riots of Central Nigeria, 1960-1964', 2007, 1960-64.

16'Annual Report Plateau Province Department Reports [1934]'.

ethnic groups, not between them, which is precisely where the most consequential conflicts occurred.

4. Non-Coercive Improvisation: The Colonial Response to Its Own Limits

The recognition that coercion was insufficient, even within the colonial administration itself, generated a range of non-coercive conflict management strategies that were improvised rather than designed. These strategies are documented across the provincial records of the 1920s to 1950s and fall into three broad categories: administrative arbitration, institutional mediation through traditional authorities, and the co-optation of educated elites.

4.1 Administrative Arbitration and Collective Punishment

The 1918 Collective Punishment Ordinance is typically read as a coercive instrument: the law authorised the fining of entire communities for crimes committed by their members.¹⁷ In the Middle Belt, however, the ordinance functioned as a hybrid mechanism that combined punitive sanction with mediatory procedure. Colonial records show that authorities used the collective punishment framework not as a substitute for force but as an alternative to it. In one documented case on the borders of Otupka District (Benue Province) and Igala District (Kabba Province), Assistant District Officer Beevor and

twelve police officers intervened to stop inter-community fighting without applying force. Administrative officers of both provinces subsequently imposed small collective fines and tried the originator of the disturbances for murder.¹⁸

The mediation component, officers of two provinces negotiating a shared penalty framework, was as significant as the punitive outcome.

The monthly meetings presided over by the Sarkin Jos in the Jos Division provided a structured forum for the airing of inter-group grievances, combining de jure tribal authorities for the whole division with de facto Hausa village headmen in a single deliberative space.¹⁹ These were not consultative meetings in any participatory sense, as colonial authority presided and decisions were imposed, but they represented a recognition that the management of intergroup tensions required a forum that coercion alone could not provide.

Periodic tours by district officers, mandated by the colonial administration, served a similar function. Officers were charged with resolving land boundary disputes on tour, disputes that were, as the Plateau Province records acknowledge, 'predominant in the colonial period because of shifts and changes in pre-colonial

17 Patrols', Endangered Archives Programme, EAP532/1/9/16; 'Benue Province, Annual Report [1931]', British Library, EAP532/1/22/2.

18 'Benue Province, Annual Report [1931]' (British Library, EAP532/1/22/2, n.d.), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-22-2>.

19 'Jos Division Plateau Province Annual Report', Endangered Archives Programme, EAP532/1/20/13.

boundaries.²⁰ The tour system acknowledged implicitly what the punitive patrol system could not: that boundary and land disputes required negotiation and adjudication, not force.

4.2 Traditional Authorities as Mandated Mediators

The most institutionally significant non-coercive mechanism was the use of traditional rulers and their representatives as mandated mediators in intergroup conflicts. The farmer-herder dispute, the most persistent and consequential intergroup conflict in the Middle Belt, provides the clearest evidence of this mediation architecture. By 1931, the Plateau Province Divisional Office had developed a formal procedure for managing herder-farmer conflicts that devolved authority to traditional intermediaries at both ends of the dispute. A Fulani herder seeking to establish a new Ruga or relocate an existing one was required to apply to the district head through his *Ardo*, the Fulani representative leader, for formal sanction.²¹ The district head, as custodian of indigenous land rights, would adjudicate the application; the *Ardo* would advocate for his community's interests. This procedure created a structured mediation space in which the authority of the indigenous district head and the representative capacity of the Fulani *Ardo* operated as

complementary rather than competing roles. It was, in institutional terms, a hybrid conflict management arrangement: state-mandated, traditionally grounded, and operating through the co-operation of two non-state community authorities.

In 1945, the appointment of a full-time land officer for the Jos Division further extended this logic. R.M. Frost's management of the overgrazing problem combined administrative regulation, including permits, cattle population limits, and grazing bans, with negotiated compliance, working through Fulani *ArDOS* and district heads rather than around them. The 1945–1949 Jos Division Annual Report documented the results approvingly: the permit system reduced the cattle population by 35%, improved relations between farming and herding communities, and generated economic cooperation between indigenes and Fulani herders.²² The success of this arrangement, in contrast to the consistent failure of punitive approaches to the same dispute, was a practical demonstration of the superiority of mediated over coercive conflict management in the Middle Belt context. It was also a structural acknowledgement of what the colonial admin-

20'Pankshin Division Bauchi Province No 49 Quarterly Report [September 30]', *Endangered Archives Programme*, April 1923, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-6-1>; 'Shendam Division Quarterly Report [September 30]', *Endangered Archives Programme*, April 1934, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-20-25>; J.M. Resident Fremantle, 'Muri Province Half Yearly Report No 100 by Resident JM Fremantle [June 30, 1917]' (British Library, EAP532/1/24/56, 1917), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-24-56>.

21'Jos Division Plateau Province No 59 Quarterly Report [September 30]', *Endangered Archives Programme* (Nigeria: British Library, April 1931), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-20-19>.

22'Jos Division Plateau Province Annual Reports [1945-1949]', *Endangered Archives Programme* (British Library, EAP532/1/20/14, n.d.), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-20-14>.

istration had learnt through four decades of experience: that inter-group conflict in the Middle Belt could not be governed through force alone. Beaton's 1944 recommendations on the Fulani settlement question made the logic of this mediation architecture explicit. His advice to the Jos Division subcommittee was that any resettlement plan must adhere to indigenous land policies; that land required for resettlement should 'not be taken forcibly to avert conflicts between the indigenes and the settlers'²³ and that a controlled grazing system, negotiated with district heads and Fulani representatives, was more viable than either forced settlement or forced exclusion. These recommendations were premised on the recognition that neither coercive dispossession nor coercive exclusion could resolve a conflict whose roots lay in competing legitimate claims to land. Only a mediated arrangement, grounded in the authority of both parties' traditional representatives, offered a pathway to sustainable management.

4.3 The Educated Elites as a Third Layer of Conflict Management

The Christian missionary-educated elite emerged as a distinct conflict management actor from the 1940s, representing the least designed element of the colonial administration's non-coercive repertoire and the most analytically distinct. Administrative arbitration and traditional ruler mediation operated at the level of specific

disputes, adjudicating between parties over defined grievances at the incident and community level. This elite group advocacy operated at a different level of formality. It addressed the political and institutional conditions that gave rise to and determined disputes over land, representation, and ethnic ownership. This distinction matters for understanding how the three mechanisms functioned together as a system rather than as parallel and interchangeable instruments. Without dispute-level mediation, systemic advocacy had no complement at the community level. The political framework that generated successive disputes could not be challenged by dispute-level mediation without systemic advocacy. The three mechanisms were differentiated responses to different dimensions of the same structural condition, and it is precisely their differentiation that makes the tripartite architecture analytically significant.

Missionary education in Plateau Province was initially orientated toward religious instruction rather than secular training, but by the late 1930s and early 1940s, it had produced a class of literate, politically conscious minority community members who occupied an institutional position that neither the colonial state nor the traditional rulership could fill.²⁴ These were advocates capable of presenting intergroup grievances in the institutional language of the colonial and regional political system, a capacity that Fulani *ArDOS* and

²³Divisional Notes Jos Division [1913] | Endangered Archives Programme', accessed 30 June 2020, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-11-9>.

²⁴Mangvwat, *History of Class Formation in the Plateau Province of Nigeria, 1902-1960: The Genesis of the Ruling*

Class; 'Plateau Province Educational Annual Reports [1942-1956]', *Endangered Archives Programme* (British Library, EAP532/1/19/59, n.d.), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-19-59>.

district heads, however effective as community mediators, did not possess and were not positioned to develop.

The tribal unions that this educated elite established, the Berom Progressive Union (BPU), the Tiv Progressive Union (TPU), the Berom Educational and Cultural Organisation (BECO), and the Non-Muslim League were not simply ethnic lobbying organisations. They performed a systemic conflict management function by channeling the economic and political grievances of Middle Belt minority communities into institutional processes, including petitions to colonial administrators, representations to the Northern House of Assembly, and legal challenges to land alienation decisions. The BPU's contestation of the Sarkin Jos chieftaincy illustrates the register at which this function operated. The dispute over whether a Hausa or Berom chief would govern Jos was not a discrete intergroup incident amenable to administrative arbitration or traditional mediation. It was a contest over the political architecture of representation itself, a conflict generated by the colonial administrative structure rather than by a specific incident between identifiable parties. By securing the appointment of Rwang Pam as Chief of Berom in 1947 through sustained institutional advocacy rather than communal violence, the BPU demonstrated that

elite contestation could redirect structurally generated political conflicts into institutional channels.²⁵ This was conflict management operating at the systemic level, addressing not a particular dispute but the political conditions that made disputes over ownership and representation structurally recurrent.

The limits of elite conflict management at this point were real and significant. The educated elites of the Middle Belt were commoners without the economic resources or organisational capacity of their northern counterparts, and their internal divisions undermined the coherence of their systemic advocacy. The differences between Plateau-orientated groups and the Benue Valley organisations, between those seeking a separate Middle Belt region and those who preferred being accommodated within the Northern structure, meant that elite advocacy addressed the political conditions of conflict unevenly and incompletely. The failure to involve all minority groups in the United Middle Belt Congress meant that some ethnic minorities opposed the elite-led agenda altogether, aligning with the NPC government for patronage reasons.²⁶ The educated elites were structurally necessary, but in organisation, they were a fragile layer of the colonial conflict management architecture, capable of systemic advocacy where community-level mediation could not reach but unable to deliver the

²⁵Logams, *The Middle-Belt Movement in Nigerian Political Development: A Study in Political Identity 1949-1967*; Philip Ostien, 'Jonah Jang and the Jasawa: Ethno-Religious Conflict in Jos, Nigeria', *Muslim-Christian Relations in Africa*, 2009, 1–42, <http://opus.ub.uni-bayreuth.de/schriftenreihen.php?la=de>.

²⁶Logams, *The Middle-Belt Movement in Nigerian Political Development: A Study in Political Identity 1949-1967*, 577–81.

political transformation that would have required a degree of elite cohesion the colonial period never produced.

4.4 From Colonial Improvisation to Postcolonial Inheritance

The claim that colonial improvisation produced an inherited architecture requires demonstrating that the three mechanisms, specifically administrative arbitration, traditional ruler mediation, and educated elite advocacy survived the transition to independence and continued to operate in the postcolonial period. The evidence for this transmission operates at two levels, the first being the immediate reproduction of the coercive deficit in the First Republic, and the second being the formal constitutionalisation of the mediation function through the local government reforms of the 1970s.

The Tiv Riots of 1960 and 1964 are the first post-colonial test of the inherited architecture and its first postcolonial confirmation. The police failure was structural and immediate. Seven NPF units and 366 Native Authority police officers proved unable to contain fifty thousand rioters, reproducing in the First Republic the same under-resourcing and ethnic delegitimation that had defined the colonial coercive deficit.²⁷ The federal government's response reproduced the colonial

sequence in precise order, with coercive escalation through military deployment; administrative arbitration through the Coomassie Commission, established in 1964; and elite advocacy through the UMBC's engagement with the commission process. The tripartite architecture was not designed for this moment any more than it had been designed for the colonial one. It was activated by the same structural condition that had produced it, namely, the inability of coercion alone to manage intergroup conflict in the Middle Belt.

The formal transmission of the mediation function occurred through the very reforms ostensibly designed to dismantle traditional authority. The military government's abolition of the Native Authority Police in 1967 and the local government reforms of 1976 stripped traditional rulers of their coercive instruments, specifically courts, prisons, and police, but Paragraph 23 of the Guidelines for Local Government Reforms explicitly preserved their peace-maintenance role, requiring chiefs to remain responsible 'in assisting government in the maintenance of peace'.²⁸ The 1979 constitution institutionalised this residual function by establishing police committees with mandatory traditional ruler repre-

²⁷Vaaseh, 'Ethnic Politics and Conflicts in Nigeria's First Republic : The Misuse of Local Administrative Police Forces (NAPFS) and the Tiv Riots of Central Nigeria, 1960-1964'; Gloria Na'antoe Longba'am, 'Historicising Hybrid Conflict Management: State and Non-State Dynamics in Nigeria's Middle Belt 1957-2018' (PhD Thesis, Makerere University, 2022).

²⁸Enyi John Egbe, 'Native Authorities and Local Government Reforms in Nigeria since 1914', *IOSR J Humanit Soc Sci* 19 (2014): 113–127.

sentation in every local government area in Nigeria.²⁹ What the 1976 reforms accomplished, in effect, was not the dismantling of the colonial mediation architecture but its constitutional clarification. Traditional rulers lost the coercive authority they had never exercised with legitimacy in the eyes of Middle Belt communities, while retaining the mediation function that had been the operative centre of colonial conflict management since the 1930s.

That function remains operative. KII 21, interviewed in Makurdi in April 2021, described its contemporary form with precision.³⁰ Ward and district heads serve as the primary security authority within their communities, vetting and organising vigilante groups whose members they know personally and liaising upward to state police and military only when local management fails. The logic of the *Ardo*/district head has not been displaced by postcolonial institutional reform, as it devolves security authority to community representatives whose legitimacy comes from ethnic custodianship rather than state appointment. It has been reproduced through it.

5. The Structural Ceiling on Colonial Conflict Management

The improvised non-coercive mechanisms examined in Section 4 shared a structural limitation that no degree of refinement could overcome. Administrative arbitration, traditional ruler me-

diation, and educated elite advocacy could manage the symptoms of inter-group conflict in the Middle Belt; they could not address its structural cause because that cause was the colonial administration itself. The same administrative apparatus that improvised these mechanisms simultaneously produced the bounded ethnic identities and spatial arrangements that made inter-group conflict structurally persistent. Understanding why the inherited architecture managed but never resolved inter-group conflict in the Middle Belt requires understanding what colonial administration built beneath it.

The dual administrative structure of eleven indigenous districts alongside four Hausa village areas created a spatial geography of ethnic belonging that was entirely colonial in origin. Before the British administrative reorganisation, the communities of the Middle Belt had fluid and overlapping social networks in which individuals participated in multiple collective identities. The colonial administration's need for a definite political unit, either a district with a recognised chief or a village area with a designated headman, replaced these fluid networks with bounded, named, and politically consequential ethnic categories. Communities that had previously coexisted through negotiated arrangements of varying formality were now organised into administrative units whose boundaries were

²⁹Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, 'Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria', § 17(3) (1979), https://www.constituteproject.org/constitution/Nigeria_1999; Egbe, 'Native Authorities and Local Government Reforms in Nigeria since 1914', 120–21.

³⁰KII 2, interview held in Makurdi Local Government, 28 April 2021.

defined by colonial law, whose authorities derived their legitimacy from ethnic identity, and whose disputes were adjudicated by courts that recognised no authority across ethnic lines.

The consequences were immediate and lasting. The principle of indigenous ownership, the right of communities recognised as indigenes of a local government area to preferential access to schools, civil service appointments, and political representation, was a colonial creation that made the distinction between 'indigene' and 'settler' the most consequential social fact in Middle Belt political life. Communities that had competed over land, water, grazing routes, and trade access found that their competition now operated within an administrative framework that formalised ethnic identity as the primary determinant of legal standing. As the Birom-Hausa contest over the Sarkin Jos position demonstrated,³¹ questions of ethnic ownership of political territory were not pre-colonial inheritances but colonial productions, and they intensified rather than diminished as independence approached. The colonial administration was aware of the contradiction it was generating. F.B. Gall's memo stated explicitly that the Hausa settlements were "strictly foreign enclaves with no jurisdiction over the pagans" and that the administration

would jealously protect indigenous land rights.³² This assurance was structurally incompatible with the four Hausa village areas whose administrative and judicial protocols the colonial administration itself had established with authority superseding those of the eleven indigenous districts. The contradiction between protecting indigenous rights and building a parallel Hausa administrative apparatus was never resolved. It was inherited at independence as the indigene-settler dichotomy that has driven intergroup violence in the Middle Belt from the Tiv riots of 1960 to the farmer-herder conflicts of the 2010s.³³

This structural condition explains both the necessity and the limits of colonial improvisation. Because the colonial administration had institutionalised ethnic difference as the organising principle of legal and political life in the Middle Belt, it required non-coercive mechanisms to manage the conflicts that institutionalised difference continuously generated. The mechanisms could not dissolve the ethnic differences they were managing because they operated within the authority structures that the colonial administration had created and consecrated. Traditional ruler mediation worked through ethnic custodians whose authority was itself a colonial con-

³¹The name 'Birom' reflects colonial administrative usage and appears in the original archival records. The community's preferred self-designation is 'Berom', which appears in their organisations (notably the Berom Progressive Union) and in post-independence scholarship. Both forms appear in this paper according to the specific context being described: 'Birom' when reproducing or summarising colonial administrative language and 'Berom' when reflecting the community's own designation or post-independence usage.

³²F.B. Gall, 'Bauchi Province Annual Report', *Endangered Archives Programme* (Nigeria: British Library, April 1921), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-13-8>.

³³Leonard Plotnicov, *Strangers to the City: Urban Man in Jos, Nigeria* (Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press, 1967).

struction. Administrative arbitration adjudicated between communities whose boundaries and identities the colonial administration had drawn. The educated elite contested the distribution of colonial-era privileges between communities whose differences colonial policy had institutionalised. The non-coercive architecture managed the symptoms of a structural condition it was constitutionally incapable of curing. It was this architecture, with its capacity for management and its incapacity for resolution, which postcolonial governments inherited.

6. Conclusion

This paper has argued that colonial policing in Nigeria's Middle Belt was primarily coercive but structurally limited and that the colonial state's response to its own coercive deficit produced the tripartite conflict management architecture that postcolonial governments inherited. That response took the form of improvised administrative arbitration, traditional ruler mediation, and educated elite advocacy, deployed not as components of a designed hybrid governance system but as necessary compensations for what force could not do. The argument carries two implications for the scholarship on colonial policing in Nigeria and for the broader study of conflict management in the region.

The first implication concerns the character of colonial policing. Existing scholarship correctly identifies colonial policing as primarily coercive and primarily serving imperial rather than community interests. This paper does not contest that characterisation, but it shows that coercion was not merely dominant; it was demonstrably inadequate for managing intergroup conflict in a

region that is as ethnically and administratively complex as the Middle Belt. The coercive deficit was not a peripheral feature of colonial policing in the region but its defining structural condition, and the non-coercive mechanisms it generated were not supplementary niceties but necessary compensations for the limits of force.

The second implication concerns the genealogy of contemporary hybrid conflict management in the Middle Belt. The colonial origins of the tripartite architecture have not been systematically traced. Scholars of contemporary Nigerian security governance have identified the structure of hybrid arrangements and mapped their post-colonial elaboration through the Civil War, the Structural Adjustment Programme, and the return to democracy in 1999, but the historical process through which the socially embedded reciprocities sustaining those arrangements were produced has not been examined. This paper supplies that process. The Tiv Riots of 1960 and 1964 reproduced the colonial coercive deficit within two years of independence, activating the inherited architecture in its precise colonial sequence of coercive failure, administrative arbitration, and elite advocacy. The local government reforms of 1976 and the 1979 constitution formalised the mediation function that colonial improvisation had produced, stripping traditional rulers of their coercive instruments while preserving their peace-maintenance role through Paragraph 23 of the Guidelines for Local Government Reforms and mandatory traditional ruler representation on local police committees. The ward and district head structures that KII 21 described in Makurdi in 2021, vetting vigilante

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groups and serving as primary community security authorities, are not postcolonial innovations. They are the colonial architecture, reproduced through successive institutional reforms rather than despite them.

Bagayoko and Hutchful have recently called for the hybrid security governance literature to develop thorough knowledge of the socially embedded forms of reciprocity that shape how security actors operate in practice. The archival record examined in this paper demonstrates that those

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embedded reciprocities were not self-generated by postcolonial communities. They were the historically specific product of colonial administrative improvisation between the 1920s and 1960, transmitted across independence through the First Republic's security crises and formalised through the constitutional reforms of the 1970s. The historical depth that the Bagayoko and Hutchful framework requires is inseparable from the colonial genealogy it has not yet undertaken. This paper has begun that undertaking.

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